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Traumatic middle meningeal artery aneurysm: a case report

INTRODUCTION: Traumatic intracranial aneurysms are rare, making up about 1% of all intracranial aneurysms. They can happen due to direct injury or blunt force, with the middle cerebral artery being the most frequent site. The middle meningeal artery (MMA) is the main artery that supplies the cranial dura mater, and, because of its location, is susceptible to damage after trauma. This article reported an unusual case of giant post-traumatic MMA pseudoaneurysm. **CASE:** A 45 year-old man was referred to our department with a history of craniectomy. He complained of non-specific headache, but neurological examination was normal. A follow-up brain CT scan identified a right temporal fossa hyperdense mass. Digital subtraction angiography diagnosed a traumatic MMA aneurysm. The patient was treated with preoperative aneurysm embolization and surgical resection. **DISCUSSION:** Traumatic MMA aneurysm is a rare presentation after head trauma. It can manifest as epidural hematoma, subdural hematoma or intraparenchymal hematoma, and sometimes resembles the present case, which was discovered incidentally. **CONCLUSION:** Pseudoaneurysm is a rare complication of MMA trauma, with late presentation. It should be considered in patients with history of traumatic brain injury and temporal fossa extra-axial mass lesion with vascular characteristics.

Keywords: Meningeal arteries, Pseudoaneurysm, Intracranial aneurysm, Middle meningeal artery, Aneurysm

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